

EFFICIENT USE OF WATER-SAVING TECHNOLOGIES

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Annotation: Several types of water-saving technologies are used in our country. Irrigation by laying a film on the ground, using flexible pipes instead of ditches, using the technology of irrigation under the soil, sprinkler irrigation, and drip irrigation are among them. For example, drip irrigation saves 20 to 60 percent of water compared to other methods. In our country, large-scale works on efficient and targeted use of water are being carried out. In particular, more than 5,000 kilometers of irrigation, 12,000 kilometers of collector-drainage, and 50,000 kilometers of canal networks are being cleaned every year.

Key words: drip irrigation, nylon, water saving, arrow, sprinkler, filtration, irrigation.

To set up a drip irrigation system, you need a water pump, a filter pond-clarifier, a fertilizer device, main and distribution pipes, irrigation hoses and auxiliary parts. Now, most of these devices and equipment are produced in our country. According to the amendments made to the Tax Code in 2014, legal entities using drip irrigation on any part of the plot of land will be exempted from paying a single land tax for a period of five years from the month of introduction of the drip irrigation system for that area. In order to introduce drip irrigation and other water-saving irrigation technologies by the Council of Ministers of the Republic of Karakalpakstan and regional working groups in 2015, the introduction of irrigation methods using drip irrigation, laying a film on the edge and portable flexible pipes a regional program was developed.

In order to implement the tasks defined in the decision of the President of Uzbekistan on December 29, 2015 "On measures for the further reform and development of agriculture in 2016-2020" and other regulatory and legal documents related to this activity, The area of spring and winter wheat will be reduced to 220,000 hectares, and it is planned to plant vegetables, sugarcane, fodder crops and intensive fruit trees on the vacated lands. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) Since 2004, these projects serve to a certain extent the implementation of the tasks defined in the decree and other regulatory legal documents on the productive use of soil and water and the diversity of crops. increasing crop productivity while solving land and water use problems aimed at maintaining soil fertility in the farm, increasing the efficient use of nutrients and water. The obtained results show that thanks to the newly demonstrated improved technologies, it is possible to increase the productivity of crops due to the use of land and water. ensured the incomes and food security

of the rural population, preserved the region's natural resources, and led to the stabilization of agriculture. At present, wheat planting rate is much higher (250 kg/ha) in the fields cultivated with cultivator. In various projects implemented by FAO, several studies have been conducted to reduce the rate of planting and increase the economy of farmers. In cotton fields, where cotton has been harvested two or three times, direct seeding in seed drills gives higher yields than traditional sowing methods, and also brings additional income. A direct sowing seeder was used to plant a number of agricultural crops such as winter wheat, sunflower, sesame, and cotton. The performance and economic indicators of the imported direct seed drills are compared with the indicators of the old (SZ-3,6) drill and are shown in the table below. If these agricultural machines (direct seed drills) were produced in Uzbekistan, farmers would get more profit from growing crops. If several technological processes such as ploughing, grinding, chiseling and planting are performed in the traditional seeder method, and 7,360 liters of fuel and lubricants were consumed for 100 hectares of cultivated area when grain was planted with a SZ-3.6 type seeder, and when wheat is planted with the new seeder that allows direct sowing, one hectare 860 liters (10 times less) of fuel and lubricants were used at the expense of the cultivated area. That is, the amount of oil products saved at the expense of 100 hectares of cultivated land was 6500 liters. If we add to the saved oil products, in addition to the cost of wages and depreciation of tractors, it can be seen that the amount of profit that the farmer receives from one hectare of land in terms of savings will be quite significant. Also, due to the decrease in the number of tractors entering the crop field for soil cultivation, the process of soil compaction will be much delayed, and in addition, it means that the yield of crops will increase. Similar results were obtained with winter wheat planted in a paddock, with a 50 percent reduction in seed use and a 30 percent reduction in water use. According to the results of the experiment, it was found that the water consumption (water use is a very important factor in Uzbekistan) in corn planted with a cotton seeder is reduced by 32%. The technology of planting cotton has been tested on winter wheat, corn, corn and other crops, and the obtained results encourage us to look to the future with confidence. If cotton seeders were developed in Uzbekistan, it would increase the area of its introduction.

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